

Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of Some Aryl Thiolacetates : A Study of the Expansion of the Valence Shell of Sulphur

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Ultraviolet absorption spectra of some aryl thiolacetates and aryl acetates have been recorded and analysed. The data indicate the possibility of the expansion of the valence shell of sulphur in *p*-anisyl thiolacetate and *p*-dimethylaminophenyl thiolacetate.

It is now generally accepted that sulphur in certain circumstances expands its valence shell by utilisation of its vacant *d*-orbitals. Recently, Cilento¹ has published a review on this subject. The theoretical significance of this problem as well as the need to find more experimental evidence in favour of *d*-orbital resonance prompted us to make a careful study of the UV spectra of some aryl thiolacetates. Cilento^{2,3} has already studied the UV absorption spectra of some thiol esters including *p*-anisyl thiolbenzoate and *p*-anisyl thiolacetate. Indeed, he came to the conclusion that in the photo-excited state of the 240 mμ transition, shown by *p*-anisyl thiol esters, sulphur utilised a *d*-orbital. Bordwell and Boutan⁴ have criticised the view of Cilento on the ground that the bathochromic shift of the first primary band, on passing from *p*-hydroxyphenyl thiolacetate to the corresponding anion, is of the same magnitude as that occurring on passing from phenol itself to the phenolate anion, and that therefore sulphur should not be concerned in this transition of *para*-substituted phenyl thiolacetates. Whether or not the following transition :

occurs to any significant extent cannot be decided by the approach of Bordwell and Boutan alone. The introduction of the *para*-methoxyl into phenyl thiolacetate molecule causes not only a bathochromic shift of the absorption maximum but also an increase in the intensity of absorption. The magnitude of this increase is also an important factor to consider.

With a view to studying further this question of sulphur utilising a *d*-orbital, we have taken the UV absorption spectra of several aryl thiolacetates. For comparison,

1. *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, 80, 147.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3748; 1954, 76, 4469.
3. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 418.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 854.

the spectra of some of the corresponding oxygen analogues were also determined. The data are recorded in Tables I and II (see also Figs. 1-4).

TABLE I

UV absorption spectra of aryl thioacetates, ArSC(=O)CH₃.

Ar.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.	Ar.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.
Phenyl	*228 m μ	3,700	<i>o</i> -Chloro	*237 m μ	5,100
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	*228	6,600	<i>p</i> -Chloro	246	11,650
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	*229	4,500	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	239	13,600
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	229	8,000	4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethylphenyl	234	8,900
2,6-Dimethylphenyl	274	1,300	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-phenyl	275	23,100
*Shoulder.					

TABLE II

UV spectra of aryl acetates, ArOCOCH₃.

Ar.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.	Ar.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\epsilon_{\max}$.
Phenyl	265 m μ	400	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	265 m μ	540
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	268	460	2,6-Dimethylphenyl	260	120
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	269	400	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	276.5	1,800
				223	7,700

The spectra of *o*-methyl-, *m*-methyl-, *p*-methyl-, *o*-chloro-, and *p*-chloro-phenyl thioacetates are very much like the spectrum of the parent compound, phenyl thioacetate. The absorption continuously increases with decreasing wave length (Fig. 1). There is, however, a shoulder in the 230-240 m μ region. The *p*-methyl group, which has an electron-releasing inductive and hyperconjugative effect, and the *para*-chlorine atom, which has an electron-releasing mesomeric effect, increase the intensity of absorption.

Phenyl acetate, *o*-methyl-, *m*-methyl- and *p*-methyl-phenyl acetates absorb less than their sulphur analogues in the 220-300 m μ region (Fig. 4). They also show in 260-270 m μ region a distinct weak absorption band which is not seen for the corresponding thioacetates. The non-appearance of this band in the case of the latter is presumably due to its being masked by the adjacent strong absorption band (seen as a shoulder). This view gains support from the spectrum of 2,6-dimethylphenyl thioacetate which shows a clear but weak absorption band at 274 m μ . This band and the one exhibited by aryl acetates in the 260-270 m μ region are undoubtedly B-bands². The masking of the B-band in the spectrum of phenyl thioacetate may be attributed to the strong conjugative interaction of the -SC(=O)CH₃ group with the benzene ring. In 2,6-dimethylphenyl thioacetate such a conjugation seems to be inhibited by the *ortho*-methyl groups and so the B-band appears.

A comparison of the spectra of *p*-dimethylaminophenyl thioacetate and *p*-anisyl thioacetate with that of phenyl thioacetate (Fig. 2) reveals the following facts. There is resemblance in the shape of the absorption curves of these compounds. The positions at which the absorption bands appear are, however, different. *p*-Dimethylaminophenyl thioacetate has a shoulder around 310 m μ , whereas *p*-anisyl thioacetate has one in the

neighbourhood of 280 $m\mu$ and phenyl thiolacetate in the 230 $m\mu$ region. *p*-Dimethylaminophenyl thiolacetate exhibits a strong band at 275 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 23,100). A similar but less intense band is exhibited by *p*-anisyl thiolacetate at 239 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 13,600). The corresponding band of phenyl thiolacetate is not fully seen within the accessible region of the spectrum, but its existence beyond 220 $m\mu$ cannot be doubted. The greater bathochromic shift and the larger hyperchromic effect observed for the *p*-dimethylamino compound are due to the high electron-releasing power of the $\cdot N(CH_3)_2$ group. It may therefore be assumed that the excited state of *p*-dimethylaminophenyl thiolacetate receives important contributions from the following structures:

FIG. 1

When a *para* electron-releasing substituent conjugates with the $\cdot SCOCH_3$ group, the difference in energy between the ground and excited states of the molecule becomes smaller

and the absorption maximum occurs at a longer wave length. In accordance with this view, 4-methoxy-3,5-dimethylphenyl thiolacetate has spectral characteristics which reveal inhibition of the conjugative interaction of MeO- and -SCOMe by the methyl groups flanking the methoxyl. It absorbs maximally at 234 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 8,900), whereas *p*-anisyl thiolacetate has absorption maximum at 239 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 13,600).

FIG. 2

The spectral behaviour of *p*-anisyl acetate offers a contrast to that of *p*-anisyl thiolacetate. Significantly, in the former there is no indication of conjugation between MeO- and -OCOMe groups. The spectrum of *p*-anisyl acetate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 276.5, 223; $\epsilon_{\max}$ 1800, 7700) is very much like that of anisole ($\lambda_{\max}$ 270, 220; $\epsilon_{\max}$ 1700, 7100).

FIG. 3

EXPERIMENTAL

All the esters used in the present investigation except the new ones, given below, were prepared as described in the literature. The spectra were determined using a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, Model DU. The solvent used was 95% ethanol.

p-Dimethylaminophenyl Thiolacetate.—*pp'*-Dimethylaminodiphenyl disulphide⁶(5g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (20 ml), glacial acetic acid (20 ml), and zinc dust (5 g.) for 3 hours. The solid separating on pouring the reaction mixture in water was filtered, washed with water, and recrystallised twice from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 80-81°, yield 83%. (Found: C, 61.42; H, 6.35. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₈ONS: C, 61.54; H, 6.67%).

2,6-Dimethylphenyl Thiolacetate.—2,6-Dimethylthiophenol⁷ was dissolved in pyridine, an excess of acetic anhydride was added, and the mixture was left overnight. The oil, obtained on pouring the mixture into water, was taken up in ether, the ether extract

6. Morz and Weith, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 403.

7. Kazimi *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2470.

was washed successively with water, sodium hydroxide solution, water, dilute hydrochloric acid, and water and dried (CaCl_2). After removal of the ether, the product boiled at $129^\circ/11\text{mm}$. The yield was quantitative. (Found: C, 86.64; H, 6.52. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{OS}$: C, 86.67; H, 6.67%).

FIG. 4

4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethylphenyl thioacetate was obtained in quantitative yield by acetylating the corresponding thiophenol⁸; b.p. $154/15^\circ\text{mm}$. (Found: C, 62.58; H, 6.71. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 62.85; H, 6.66%).